

TRANSLATION PROCESS OF THE BOOK CALLED “WUTHERING HEIGHTS” INTO UZBEK LANGUAGE.

Atoboyeva Aziza Muhiddin qizi

National University of Uzbekistan Foreign Philology Faculty

2nd year student. otaboyeva_a@nuu.uz

Yusupova Shukrona Olimjon qizi

missolimjonovna@gmail.com

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There is no doubt that translating works from European languages into Uzbek brings some difficulties. The main reason for this is not only the differences in the characteristics of the two nations, but also the family of Uzbek and European languages. It is a language belonging to the Turkic group of the Altaic language family, and English is a language belonging to the Germanic group of the Indo-European family. Of course, in such a case, word forms and sentence construction together with adverbs also differ.

Emily Brontë's "Wuthering Heights" has not been translated into Uzbek before. The work depicts British life in the 18th century. The work is written in a romantic spirit, and its characters act radically towards each other.

During the translation of the work, it was realized that the words used in ordinary speech in Uzbek and English differ from each other. That is, the phrase "jin ursin" spoken in Uzbek is expressed in the English language with the devil mixed in it.

Also, some words cannot be directly translated into English. For example, the word Joseph is translated into Uzbek as "Yusuf". But there is a big difference between Prophet Yusuf recognized by Uzbeks, that is, Muslims, and Joseph mentioned in the Bible. The main reason is that the actions and deeds of "Yusuf" mentioned in the Qur'an and "Joseph" mentioned in the Bible are different.

Transcription and transliteration methods were also used in the translation process. In the process of translation of special nouns, their alternative version in Uzbek language was added. As for the translation of the names, the main characters and episodes of the work were translated using the method of transcription. The main reason for this is that some difficulties were encountered in the pronunciation of the names when they were translated into Uzbek using the transliteration method.

First of all, the relationship between Catherine and Heathcliff will not be good from the beginning. The main reason for this is that Heathcliffe was simply a gypsy and a servant brought by Catherine's father. Their social origins are

definitely different. The friendship between them grows stronger and later turns into a strong love. But Catherine could not see the success of this love, and for this reason, she wants to live not with Heathcliff, but with Ornsshaw. It is unclear whether Catherine chose to live here for her own interests and a better life in the future, or whether she decided to help Heathcliff. The events of the play are arranged in such a way that Heathcliff, who could not even earn the status of an ordinary servant at the beginning, eventually takes away all the wealth from Catherine and her brother. Yes, of course, in this way, he will attack his love and those who humiliated him.

One of the difficulties encountered in the process of translating the work into Uzbek is to express the feelings of two young people for each other. That is, in Uzbek language, when young people give in to strong emotions based on their mentality, it is morally wrong and they feel it. They try to express not physical, but internal optimistic feelings more.

Here are a number of questions that will torment the reader: Why did Mr. Lockwood not want to help Cathy, knowing her condition? What did the writer want to achieve by connecting the fate paths of Herit and Katie? Why is Hindley, the child of such a strong man, weak and weak, why did fate give such a fate to his father? There are too many questions.

Geographical locations during the translation of the work may be familiar to students who have been reading the masterpieces of world literature before, but it is difficult to immediately visualize hills and hills that are windy all year round. But for many, the concept of strong and consuming love is associated not with Romeo and Juliet, but with Heathcliff and Catherine. The castle "Wuthering Heights", the novel of the main characters, the English nature - add a special charm to this work.

